

Social Service Camping An Opportunity; To Develop Social and Moral Values in Students: A Case Study

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Abstract

Social service or social work is the work done by individual for the benefit of society. It should be aimed to promote social change or development in the society. It includes the principle based on social justice, human rights and the responsibility of each citizen with respect to the diverse social culture of our country. Students studying in schools are the future of our country. They are going to develop our country in the near future. When they will grow up and become professionals, they will work for the betterment of country. So these should know to interact socially and morally, How to understand other's problems and how to work something better for society. Social service in the schools is a specialized area concerned with various activities like help the homeless, clean the environment, beautification of school building,strengthening the social skills, emotional intelligence ,relationship building, social awareness towards superstitions and social evils etc. The paper presents a case study of social work done by students of Jawahar Govt.Sr.Sec.School kuchaman City during the social service camp and apart from the camp. It focuses on the activities conducted by students which to be a blue stone to develop socio-moral values in the students at school level. It also provides a view to other students towards social work.

Keywords Social Service, Clean Environment, Socio-Moral Values, Relation Ship Building, Skills, Beautification.

Introduction

In ancient India the nature of social service was that of charity. The earliest reference to charity to be found in the Rig Veda. Which encourages charity by saying "May the one who gives, shine the most" Modern social work was introduced in India by christial missionaries in the beginning of the 19Century. When they making homes for orphans and destitutes. Indian social reformers like Sasipada Banerjee, Phule, Karve too started homes for widows. During the medieval period some rulers introduced reforms while prominent reforms in the modern period worked to abolish evils like 'Sati- Pratha' and promote education as well as women's rights. Formal social work training began in 1930s and numerous organizations have contributed to the development of social service in India. To Gandhi, the individual was as important if not more, then the society as he firm believed that the happiness of the individual formed the constituents part of the happiness of the society. So for him, social welfare meant the conscious submission of the individual and a voluntary contribution of one's possession to the society, which consisted of all, not a majority and in return, the social system built upon the principles of non-violence and democracy, was to give a complete guarantee for the maximum development of the individual's personality. According to Mahtma Gandhi, Belief in god, truth, ahimsa, morality, ethics of life, dignity of labour, justice, equality, liberty and fraternity; All these values help in building an ideal society. Therefore, Gandhi wanted the youth to the villagers and imbibe morally superior values. To Gandhi the youth are the agents of social change. They have the capacity to establish an ideal society based on the immortal principles of truth and non-violence. The main aim of education is universal development of a student but social service also assists the personality development. In Indian schools, social service scheme was launched in Gandhi ji's centenary year, 1969.Aimed at developing student's personality through community service. To develop the social and moral values in students

along with the personality development, Rajasthan government have included 'Socially useful productive work (SUPW) and social service' in syllabus of class 9th and 10th. A 15 day social service camp is also organized every year for the students of class 12th in summer vacations. It is necessary for all the schools of Rajasthan board of secondary education. A social service camp was also organized in Jawahar Govt. Sr.Sec.School Kuchaman City from 17th May to 31st May under the supervision of Dr.Bhanwar Lal and Mr.Zaheer Khan.It was monitored by block chief education officer Mr.Jagdish Roy and principal Mrs Manju Choudhary.

Objective of study

Objectives in general are the statements or formulations, what we seek to achieve. Educational policy and accreditation standard on objectives of social service states: Social service practice promotes human well- being by strengthening opportunities, resources and capacities of people in their environments and by creating policies and services to correct conditions that limit human rights and the quality of life. In case of school students to develop socio-moral values, social service and camping are the golden opportunities. Various efforts are made to achieve the objectives by enabling students to function in society. The objective of camping is to create a sense of social welfare among the students.

The objectives of social service and camping in this case study, are as follows:

1. To concern with social life.
2. To inspire selfless service.
3. To understand the community in which they work.
4. To preparing for participating in social activities.
5. To practice national integration social harmony.
6. To develop skills for collective living.
7. To identify the needs and problems of community and help in their solution.
8. To inculcate respect for democratic values.
9. To develop among themselves a sense of social and civic responsibilities.
10. To create a sense of mutual cooperation.
11. To generate labour loyalty.
12. To create environmental awareness.
13. To facilitate effective utilization of community resources for their welfare.
14. To develop a constructive skill.
15. To help in social adjustment.
16. To provide socio-legal aid to needy people.
17. To develop and use research, knowledge and skills that advances social service.
18. To create health awareness.

A social service camping should provide a variety of learning experiences through social engagement and participation of students. Teacher should recognize the potential of students and use it for social service.

Review of Literature

Every educational institution has some specific goals along with achievements, for universal development of the students. Development of social, cultural, ethical, behavioral and moral values in the students are some special goals for educational institutions. Out of these social and moral values are very important for any youth because it is fact today, there is a social & moral decadence. There are several cases that were done by the teenagers or students of schools and colleges, such as crime, violence, abusing, married by accident, bullying, gangster, stealing, gambling, free sex, college ragging, stabbing, robbery, threatening, and misbehavior with parents and elders. Recently an incident of stabbing took place among 7th class students in Lakhisarai, India (Etv Bharat Bihar,2024).In which three students were seriously injured. Similarly one student stabbed another after hearing a minor incident in Delhi, India (Aajtak.in,2023) The question is why it can be happen? I believe that the social and moral decadence at our environment being the cause. According to National Crime Record Bureau of India 20% youth are committing suicide due to lack of social and moral support. One of reason for this may be that, in present culture milieu children are reared increasingly in toxic environment that pose special challenges for their moral and social development (Gabarino,2004; Quart,2003). Such as any decline in social and moral values can be dangerous for our future generations. So we should analyze, what social values are lacking in the students (Peter k.Jonason et al.,2015).

Before we focus on development of social and moral values in the students, we have to know what are social and moral values?. Social values are defined as standards which individuals and social groups employ to define personal goals and essentially shape the nature and form a social order in collective I.e., what is acceptable and not acceptable, what ought or not to be, what is desirable or non-desirable (Kluckhohn,1951). Social values also refers to human principles that are essentially desirable for the wellbeing of an individual, a group or a society. Some important social values are Truth &Honesty, Generosity, Patriotism, Respect for seniors and elders, Justice & Kindness, Tolerance,

Cooperation and Excellence. These public values are integral to the very nature of the social sciences (John D. Brewer,2018). In same way to know about the moral values we should learn about morality. Morality is derived from the Latin word 'mores' which means "manners" or "morals". In the words of Amingo and Nwaokugha (2006); morality is "an accepted code of human conduct in a society". Morality entails "having laws that will regulate dealing of men who can choose to abide by these laws because they know it is good sense to do so"(Uyanga and Amingo,2010). Such as morality make the men moral. Moral values are defined as guidelines that assist a person in deciding between right and wrong. In order to create honest credible, fair judgement, relationship in daily life and the awareness of one's morals along with self-awareness is crucial. Truthfulness and respect of others are the most important moral values, which made the students more social. In order to achieve the desired goals and objectives, the individuals need to recognize the meaning and significance of truthfulness and honesty(Connors C.D.,2016). We know that truthfulness grows from the roots of trust. Trust is an another important moral value, which connects the people together. It is chicken soup of social life. It brings us all of the good things from a willingness to get involved in our communities to higher rate of economic growth and ultimately to satisfaction with government performance (Putnam,1993,1995; Fukuyama,1995; Knack and Keefer,1997), to making daily life more pleasant. Trust is a multifaceted concept. Mostly it is conceived as a "rational" response to trustworthy behavior by others (Eric M. Uslaner,2001). Therefore,trust can become the biggest factor for the success of students.

In ancient time elders were respected because they had knowledge and wisdom. They also taught the youngsters, lesson of sociality and morality. But presently social and moral values are continuously declining. Which is dangerous not only for any society, country but also for whole world. Therefore, it is the responsibility of all of us to make students & youth social and moral because it has been stated and rightly so too that the future of any nation rests on the shoulders of youth of today and tomorrow (Dr,Ime N. George & Unwanaobong,D.Uyanga,2014).Moral development influences the student's achievements and behavior.Moral values have to be taught to the students at school level and also at their houses (Nurlaela Sari,2013).In my view social and moral values together can be developed in children initially in their families and then in society by proper guidance of elders. After that it is responsibility of schools and colleges. The schools & colleges should taught the books of social and moral knowledge with their regular curriculum. It is ironic that many schools and colleges are not doing this. We must not forget that competitive exams have turned students in to robots. In such a situation, it would be meaningless for them to be social and moral. We should also take the help of technology and multimedia platforms to socialize & moralize students. Advances in technology have also facilitated innovative approaches to studying morality, such as virtual reality experiments exploring moral dilemmas (Begne et al.,2022). I have emphasized in my research that 'along with studies, social camps should be organized for school students'. These camps should be organized with socially backward or needy people, so that students can understand their life closely and can help them. In this way the social service camping will be able to establish social and moral values in the lives of students.

Research Gap

Review of literature reveals that many researches are done related to development of social and moral values in the students. Also lot of researches are made separately on importance of social and moral values in human life. The most researches emphasize on the development of these values through teaching in class rooms. But I have inculcated social and moral values in the students through social service camping, organized with needy people. That differentiates it from other researches.

Future Perspective

This research offers a bigger vision for the future. Because it is based on the principle of learning by helping, learning by watching and learning while living with the underprivileged. When students come in contact with needy people during social service camping, they understand their problems better and help them in every possible way. Due to which they develop quality of understanding people's feelings and serving them. In this way they learn the first lesson of sociality and morality. So researcher hopes all the educational institutions will conduct such camps for their students. Researcher hopes voluntary organizations working in the field of social reforms will also be able to organize such camps for those youths who are out of schools and colleges.

Analysis

Social Service Programme and Activities

An organized service or activity designed to improve social conditions in a community, as assistance to poor, troubled families and needy people.

The programs and activities conducted under social service are as follows:

A.Regular Activities Some regular programs and activities are continuously run by students in school campus and in adopted slum for betterment of social life. Students work for 120 hours every year under regular activities. They provide 4 hours in a week after school time.

a.Campus Beautification Work-A well maintained school provides a safe and attractive learning environment for students. School projects can offer much more than physical improvements to the school buildings and grounds. Student cleaned and painted school building from outside and inside. Students created an attractive learning environment by removing graffiti from walls, picking up litter and garbage and even planting new trees and flowers.

b.National days and celebrations -Students celebrate some important days every year like-National youth day, National girl child day, International women's day, Republic day, International social justice day, World environment day, World wild life day, World water day, National technology day, International yoga day, India's independence day, World nature conservation day, International literacy day, Elderly day, National education day, Human rights day, Indian constitution day, AIDS day etc. Students also celebrate the birth anniversaries of some great personalities like Savitri Bai Phule, Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose, Dr. Baba Saheb Ambedkar, Mahtma Gandhi, Lal Bahdur Shastri and Pandit Jawahar Lal Nehru to get valuable education from their lives.

c.National Calamities and National Emergencies-Students create awareness among the people towards the natural calamities like- Ativrushti(deluge), Annavrushti, Hail fall, Earthquake, Pandemic and Land slide through rallies, helping them during disaster. During COVID-19 pandemic students warned people about caution and explained about vaccination.

d.Establishment of Book Bank and a Library- A book bank has been established by the government in the school by providing free books and magazines for class 1st to 12th. All the arrangement of this book bank are made by students of social service. They distribute books and magazines to required students by keeping a proper record. It teaches students management skills.

e.Environmental Conservation Programs-Environmental conservation prevents environmental degradation. The world's ecosystems are each home to a range of species. When an environment is damaged or destroyed this threatens the local population's survival. Plants and animal often struggle and die when they lose their usual resource. These deaths impacts the ecosystem's biodiversity. Students of Jawahar School are running a unique program 'MERA KUCHAMAN HO HARA BHARA' for environmental conservation. Students have so far planted 2000 saplings in kuchaman City under this program. LNT company is supporting this program. The students distribute 400 cloth bags to the vegetable and fruit vendors every month to save environment from plastic.

f.Human Welfare Programs-Human welfare include work on illiteracy education, health nutrition, sanitation, hygiene, legal literacy, social justice, child welfare, social empowerment, family welfare, de-addiction, savings campaign, first aid knowledge, gender justice, campaign against social evils, crime awareness etc. These programs were organized by students in collaboration with relevant departments in adopted slum 'Gadiya Lohar Basti Kuchaman City'.

B.Camping Activities The aim to the camping program is to bring youth face to face with the community and make effort to improve their life. Students of social service are to devote 75 hours in camping activities for development of adopted slum. Students made slum dwellers aware by organizing many activities during the camp.

a.Awareness on Consumer Protection- Consumer awareness is the level of knowledge and understanding that individuals have about their rights, responsibilities and the information necessary to make informed choice in the marketplace. This knowledge is crucial so that people can make smart decisions and pick the best option for themselves. Students along with the police officers provided legal information to slum dwellers and held talks with lawyers on consumer protection.

b.Awareness Towards the Eradication of superstitions and social evils- To provide for the prevention of dreadful superstitions practices of blind faith and belief in the name of so called divine, supernatural or magical power and to bring social awareness and awakening in the society with a view to protect the people against the evil and sinister practices for the sake of exploiting. Education is the most important to eradicating superstitions and other social evils. School and college can help students develop a scientific attitude and think logically and rationally. Social service can prove to be a great

weapon in removing superstitions and social evils. Students campaign against superstitions and social evils in adopted slum and motivated the people to avoid these. They also educated people not to do child marriage. On a day of camp students organized a health checkup program in collaboration with district hospital kuchaman city and an NGO kuchaman vikas samitte, in which health of students, teachers, and people checked by Dr.Surendra Jiloya, B.L.Rulaniya and Awani Sharma. Dr.Jiloya (psychiatrist) educated the people there is no a divine or magical power so in case of any such disease should take treatment from a doctor.

c.Protection of Cultural Heritage and Cleaning of Public Places- Heritage is anything that is considered important enough to be passed on to the future generations. Cultural heritage refers to the cultural aspects like heritage sites, monuments, folklore, traditional activities and practices, language etc. During the social service camp, students cleaned the historical salt-lake of Kuchaman City and understood the making salt. Students cleaned 600year old Shakambhari Mata temple situated near Kuchaman City. Students clean bus station, railway station, police station hospital etc.,as part of social service.

d.Providing Information of Government Schemes-

The social security schemes in India and Rajasthan aims to provide financial and health protection to individuals. It offers social support to families during various life stages and in times of need. There is a comprehensive system implemented by the governments of India and Rajasthan. It ensures the well-being and welfare of society. The schemes encompass a range of initiatives that address different aspects of social security. This includes healthcare, education, employment, housing, agricultural and income support. Students informed to people about the schemes of Government of India like-Ayushman Bharat yojana, PM Poshan Shakti Nirman Abhiyan, Start Up India scheme, Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan, National Nutrition Mission, Jan Dhan Yojana, Ujjwala Yojana, Digital India Mission , Manrega Yojana, Atal Pension Yojna etc. Students also provided the information of Rajasthan Government's schemes for social welfare like Anuprati Yojana,Palanhar Yojana,Chiranjeevi Yojana,Indira Rasoi Yojana etc.

e.Awareness About Voting- Voter awareness is crucial for a healthy democracy, as informed and engaged citizens are more likely to participate in elections and make informed choices. Students of social service motivated the people of adopted slum to participate in election process and to vote. Students motivated the people aged 18 to register their names in to electoral rolls.

f.Nursing Care of the Sick-Nursing encompasses autonomous and collaborative care of individuals of all ages, families, groups and communities, sick or well and in all settings. Nursing includes the promotion of health, prevention of illness, and the care of ill, disabled and dying people. Students of social service distributed fruits to 75 mental patients living in 'Apna Ghar Ashram' in Kuchaman City and cared them. Student also provided food to people living in old age home and set an example of humanity.

g.Service to Mute Animals and Birds –Animals and birds do control and balance our environment. They have a great importance in our lives. Animal are important in our daily life as well as for purposes, for providing us food, clothing, help in our works. Birds are part of food chain. They keep a check on the over population of rodents, insects and even snake. Therefore we should serve these creatures. Respecting this sentiment, social service students provided green fodder to animals and water to birds.

Importance of Social Service and Camping For Students

It fosters invaluable life skills, cultivates empathy and empowers students to become protective agent to change community service, provides the perfect avenue for students to bridge the gap between theory and practice, helping them apply their knowledge and skills to address real world challenges. Some significances are-

- i.Students can utilize their time by doing social service for betterment of society.
- ii.When students help the needy people through various ways then they feel immense satisfaction.
- iii. Social service provides motivation to the students, while participating in social work, they have to complete their task When they complete the whole task, feel motivated.
- iv. Working interestingly some characteristics and skills are developed in students like-Communication, Critical thinking, Cultural competence, Self-care, Organization, Active Listening, Patience, Professional efficiency, Spirit of humanity, Advocacy, Team spirit etc.
- v. Students become able to understand the problems of society.
- vi.It gives rise to problem solving approaches.
- vii.Helping needy people awakens the tendency to accumulate wealth.

Challenges Faced During Social Service:

Social service is a challenging task; When a social worker goes to the field, he faces many problems. In this case study students also faced some problems doing social work. Which are as following-

- i.Lack of means of transport in adopted slum.
- ii.Lack of time.
- iii.Lack of support specially to girl students from their parental side.
- iv.Students faced negative attitude of some drug and alcohol addicted people.
- v.Students also faced the problem of child abuse.
- vi.Negative thinking of people.
- vii.Students faced some questions of people during survey like-Why we provide our personal information for you?
- viii.Felt lack of toilets and bathrooms during the visit of slum.

Literacy Survey 2022-23

During social service students conducted a literacy survey of 38 families located south of the school campus. A total of 152 people (62 males and 90 females) were found illiterate. Out of these, students made 40 males and 65 females literate. Thus they got 64.5% and 72.2% success in making male and female literate respectively. Shown as in table-1 and in fig. 1-

Table – 1 (Literacy Achievements 2022-23)

Candidate	Illiterate	Literate	Achievements
Male	62	40	64.5%
Female	90	65	72.2%

Figure - 1

Literacy Survey 2023-24

During session 2023-2024 students also conducted an age wise literacy survey of 67 families located west of the school campus. A total of 259 people (116 males and 143 female) were found illiterate, age - wise mentioned in table-2 & Fig.2. Out of these, students made 89 males and 112 females literate. Thus they got over all 76.72% and 78.32% success in making male and female literate respectively. Shown as in table- 2 and in fig.3.

Age group	Illiterate		Literate		Achievement	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Literacy of male	Literacy of female
6-14	01	04	01	04	100%	100%

15-30	23	30	18	25	78.26%	83.33%
31-45	50	65	40	50	80%	76.92%
Above 45	42	44	30	33	71.42%	75%

Table-2 (Literacy Achievements 2023-24)

Figure - 2

Figure - 3

Here male and female of 6-14 group are completely literate by students because they were easy available at home and show more interest in learning. In both above cases literacy percentage of females is better than the males because they are housewives who easily find time to study after household chores. Whereas men go to out to earn money, hence they did not show more interest in studying.

Conclusion

It has been proved from above study that students can make a good contribution in making people literate for betterment of society. Students from all societies come to a school are directly connected even with a remote family. Where it is little difficult for a government. So they can help the people easily. Today’s students are tomorrow’s doctors, engineers, teachers, leaders, businessmen etc. Hence it is necessary for them to be more social and more skilled. The role played by the students in social service at school campus and in adopted slum ‘Gadiya Lohar Basti’ reflects the channeling of youth power. Students whose only job is study did social work brilliantly and learned the lesson of empathy along with morality, serving the needy people. They also conducted surveys on tobacco addiction as well as illiteracy with accuracy and alerted the people to get rid of any addiction. This awakened the spirit of social reform among the students. Service to the sick and needy people developed moral qualities in to them. Students awakened the people on

superstitions and social evils during the camping, which made them more social. They succeeded in explaining the importance of environmental conservation and nature protection. Such as sense of social responsibility and practice of citizenship developed in students along with various skills. We know that a country of people with social and moral things is great; these are also the identity of India. But there has been a decline in values, socially and morally in India for few decades. Therefore it is important to moralize the coming generations. It can be started with school students. Social service camping is good tool for this work. Which shape students in to gentle humans who are beautiful inside out.

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